

THE STUDENTS WRITTEN OF WORK STATEMENT TO BE DONE CIRCLE KNOWLEDGE, SKILL AND QUALIFICATIONS DEVELOPMENT ISSUE

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ABSTRACT

The ability to express an opinion in written form is a complex process. Because the whole thought is the expressed text. For example, the purpose of mother tongue education is embodied in this parameter. The skills and competences acquired by the learner in the process of mother tongue education are also reflected in the text he creates. Therefore, the teacher, when evaluating the result of the quality of education based on this parameter, is determined by the state of these skills acquired by the student: a) expression of the thought in a logical consistency; b) thinking, level of complexity of the subject (simple, complex, concrete, abstract, etc.); c) relevance of the description to the topic and the value of the description; g) level of appropriate use of language means of expression in the description; d) the quality of spelling (written) literacy. It can be seen that students create text and work on the text takes a central place in the second and fourth stages of training and assignments given outside the classroom.

The program gives the teacher a full opportunity to easily replace all the texts in the textbook according to his taste, demand, convenience of the situation, to build the teaching process on the basis of literal creativity and research. Students to create must has been texts one how many is different. Of them the main ones:

- 1. The training is in progress harvest done knowledge and skill in practice supporting text Create. Such texts two and three out of the question consists of to be, in the form of a monologue and a dialogue, briefly image or story in the form of to be can _ Theirs sure shape teacher _ under the leadership of of the student himself to choose need _*
- 2. Given topic based on image (small essay) creation. Such images written and sweet tooth in appearances of students young and qualification level suitable content and in volume execution it is necessary*
- 3. Essay text higher appearance _ _ The program is as follows essay of types to use aims at : a) scientific essay (language , history , biology and another for each subject from the subjects*

special has been something topic or issue open); b) scientific and artistic essay (fiction work , writer creativity , literary processes to the analysis dedicated essays); c) artistic and creative essays (art his work from learning of the student harvest did personal experiences image); g) descriptive essay (thing , person , scene and etc to the image dedicated essay); d) free in the subject essay.

Text on work mother language in training sessions main place possession because , at the beginning of the 8th grade, " Creative text Essay and his types » section included . This is the section students in grades 1-7 text on take went their work summarize them high in classes somewhat complicated has been essay on to work prepares .

We know that the essay – the main criteria determining the students' level of creative thinking, worldview, and the possibilities of using literary language norms in speech situations. That is why it is very important to explain to the reader the textual errors made in writing the essay and the reasons for their origin. Many sources were consulted in order to study the theoretical foundations that help to understand textual errors and their causes, to prevent and eliminate textual errors. The analysis of sources showed that A. Aliyev, S. Dolimov, S. Ismatov, Q. Ahmedov, B. Turdiyev, O. Madayev, K. Kasimova, R. Abdulhatova, N. Shukrullayeva, R. Inog'omova, N. We witnessed that some aspects of teaching students to write essays were covered in Sattorova's dissertations and methodical manuals.

As a result of the study and analysis of many sources, we learned that there are knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies that are constantly and continuously needed in teaching the content and structure of the text, and they are classified on the basis of the following 4 groups: a) external organization of the essay - technical knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies; b) knowledge, skills, qualifications and competences related to aspects of content-logical description of written work (essay) ; d) knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies related to the task-spiritual types of paragraphs in the text; e) knowledge, skills and competencies related to text creation [1; p. 76].

When it comes to *the aspects of the content-logical description of the written work* , first of all, it involves creating various syntactic devices, defining their limits, and using punctuation marks for this purpose; secondly, to justify the opinion put forward in the written work, to derive from life experience in the process of writing; thirdly, it is necessary to analyze the knowledge, skills, skills and competences related to *the use of words and synonyms in the text* .

In the text **the issue** of creating various syntactic devices, defining their limits, using punctuation marks for this purpose is considered the most important in creating a text. To do this, students should be instructed to use punctuation marks to define the boundaries of independent sentences, syntactic units in the sentence, i.e., impulse, separated sentence, introductory word, introduction, etc. in particular, it is necessary to pay attention to the difference from each other, independent sentences in the text are simple sentences, compound sentences, imperative sentences, separate clause sentences, excerpted sentences, self-explanatory sentences, dialogic sentences, introductory sentences the possibility of sentences with introductory clauses, simple clauses with simple clauses in the text, simple clauses with compound clauses, compound clauses with simple clauses, simple clauses with abstract clauses, noun clauses with simple clauses, noun clauses with compound clauses with a clause, with a simple or compound clause, separated by a period, a question mark, an exclamation mark, a

colon, sometimes three periods, a comma, a dash, The need to separate characters such as parentheses should be given as *knowledge*. This same knowledge is transformed into the following *skills through practical work*: a) *to be able to form independent sentence types, to be able to separate them from the text, to be able to differentiate between them; b) separate two sentences by putting a period, question mark or exclamation mark, sometimes double marks, depending on the content, tone, purpose of expression.* Knowing and being able to apply them in practice is very important in the process of creating a text, because they are important in making a meaningful and logical statement. *The ability* to separate the punctuation marks learned in the educational stages from each other, taking into account the types of independent sentences when creating the text is formed. Therefore, working on this knowledge, skills and abilities is carried out in a certain sequence, depending on the passage of some topics in the 5th-9th grades. Taking into account that some textual errors are typical and persistent, it is necessary to plan that the concepts defined on the basis of the textbook are practically studied relatively early. Do it increase for while the following exercises choose must will be _ To such exercises the following input can:

- written in the text of words the limit right setting, necessary pause signs right to put
- in the text given of words what types of sentences that determine , then down left pause signs right to put
- text contained syntactic of devices from each other the difference to determine the difference interpretation, applied pause signs explanation;
- text contained syntactic devices right reading, to the tune looking which type of sentence that interpretation, applied pause of signs put on reasons explanation. So , that's it such as from exercises to use continuity and unity principle based on gradual done increase because it is necessary of students oral and written speech grow up issue mother language education in front standing constant from problems is considered

Creative written at work *before pushed the idea justification and him statement in doing life from experience come output* , word _ to use and textual from synonyms use issue is also important is counted . For example , creative written at work own _ thoughts right statement do , cited basis and of evidence mistake to be or life to the truth opposite arrival , word to use some cases of the text common content right to understand interrupt to give , sometimes mental stupidity cause release of the text to the content serious negative effect shows . That's why for the students _ different syntactic devices make up , their the limit mark , that's it on purpose pause signs to use to teach with one in line creative written at work before pushed the idea justification and him statement in doing life from experience come to exit to teach very necessary . _ for this in students First , the letter At the beginning of statement done that's the first thing paragraph for main thought be counted and him next sentences through open to give , justify necessity , the real reality to the students sure the eye to the front to bring , life from experience use necessity and reported thoughts to the truth near to be necessity , when composing a sentence of the word meaning , sentence the content of the real reality with relatively see , the word with it connecting another word with one get or one that he can't considerate to be , statement being done of your opinion accuracy attention focus etc about *knowledge* is given

Students to them given this knowledge learning and listen get result first reality sure imagination to do aspiration and thought express , written work from writing before want to use has been of his words the meaning explanatory from dictionaries used without him identify get and in the sentence right to use such as *to skills* have being goes. It's a skill a draft of a text (for example , an essay) . a copy preparation in the process consistency with life the truth right understanding and in observation maintenance , being created in the text and under construction in sentences of words meanings knowing and right to use *qualification* turning around goes _ In this regard the following the word apply with related this aspects always mother language of the teacher attention in the center to be necessary : a) from the real reality of the word long the meaning means ; b) thesis through the clause in place understood of your opinion next sentences through without development stay _ So, in the students word to use with depends knowledge and of skills qualification as formation each in class to practice increased to go provision is required . Each _mother language in class student which the rule on It doesn't work , of course to the text face will come . To be done grammar analyzes also talk and text based on take will go Also written of work analysis next in the process in the essay exactly so error and to a disadvantage road not to put for this in the essay makes sense statement to do with depends error and of shortcomings analysis transfer a must This is the most many p to the error road put , basically , the same one the word in every sentence or in between repeat and repeat is to use . We think so to the error road placed essay in class to everyone listening by reading to give through meaning necessary . In this , students exactly so the error repeat and repeat used by finding the word showing they give Such an error eliminate reach while textual from synonyms use through eliminate will be done . That's exactly it the situation students _ with together practical the work through done increase to the goal according to Again in this applied the word another word with replacement to the movement falls.

the students above counting passed skill and qualifications in formation written works (essay) . from transfer before one series practical exercises perform It should be for students given to the word textual synonyms find and them that's it word instead of put is to say. So practical to exercises mother language in their classes very many p applied in the exercise mistakes correction from work use to the goal according to [2; page 34.]. That 's right exercises basically spelling and pause to the signs circle mistakes eliminate in doing and spelling literacy in raising regularly using come , but this essay in the text occurring word eliminate repetition _ in reaching use also gives good results . This is the main thing attention practical exercise for selected in the text the word repetition with depends mistakes correction task by doing given , his instead of suitable coming of pronouns or meaningful from words sonny put edit text assignment they do . Regular such practical work perform independent respectively who writes statement , essay and essay such as written things in writing exactly the word repetition with depends to the error road not to put qualification formation help will give .

For example , mother language in their classes to the students textual of synonyms one word from repetition get rid of doer tool that meaning is an important issue and in this , not only , pronoun and meaningful words , perhaps connectives , some assistants , downloads , various meaning representing , this including place and moment the meaning denotative word forms , auxiliary compounds and of ravishes syntactic synonyms surface bringer attention to aspects focus need. These tools the first in the sentence expression done of action through the

second sentence to be reported to action relatedness reflection in progress , independent sentences or in paragraphs reflection reached reality is in the next sentence of reality previous in the sentence reality because of happen to be , place -time or cause and effect relations display or in general personal of your opinion in expression is used . Essay in the text independent sentences and paragraphs connect access words, entries and expressions using done is increased . And these are of the text substantive and structural wealth provides . Creative written at work the word to use and textual from synonyms use issue when it comes to , in the text time , inclination , ratio attitude in expression paragraphs organize doer of verbs form suitability from memory not to issue it is necessary Students to know must has been one series knowledge they are also students road to put possible has been of mistakes prevention in getting important importance occupation is enough

In this place to emphasize must be written of work statement to be done with depends knowledge , skill and qualifications formation constant respectively write an essay organizational and technical aspects with depends knowledge, skill and qualifications formation with organic way done increase to the road to put very important importance occupation is enough About this thoughts O.Madayev, A.Sobirov , Z.Kholmanova , Sh.Tashmirzayeva , G.Ziyodullayeva , M.Shamsiyevalar by written " Written the work types : essay , statement and dictation " is methodical in the manual to wake up can It is organizational and technical and content-logical aspects about generalized description given to them _ the following enters :

- write an essay (written ish) is beautiful thank you with sure and right _ writing necessity;
- essay text (written the work text) to the topic suitable plan based on statement to be done necessity;
- essay written the work as of the text main sign was _ substantive to the whole have to be necessity;
- in an essay (written the work in the text) methodical unity and expressiveness action of doing too _ importance;
- the idea to express for the words sure choose, sentences simplicity compliance to do need;
- write an essay (written of work) volume in terms of demand to be need;
- essay (written the work of the text) of the text substantive in parts according to respectively to paragraphs separate and letter from the beginning require writing _ important
-

Also knowledge, skills and skills checked when evaluated the following four to the parameter relies on : a) spelling mistakes ; b) pause signs error ; d) methodological errors ; e) logical errors [3; pp. 52-58].

So, first of all , the students write an essay organizational and technical aspects circle knowledge , skill and qualifications formation it is necessary And this in students *write an essay (written of work) is meaningful and logical statement to be done aspects in the text of paragraphs functional-spiritual types and text Create* with depends knowledge, skill and of competencies formation possibility creates _ *Essay (written of work) is meaningful and logical statement to be done aspects in the text of paragraphs functional-spiritual types and text Create* with dependent _ conic and of qualifications formation the next one is *in the county of paragraphs functional-semantic types* with depends knowledge , skill and qualifications formation enable will give . *In*

Mant of paragraphs functional-semantic types with dependent knowledge, skill and qualifications formation last step - text Create with depends skill and of qualifications formation take will come.

Summary by doing to say maybe it is knowledge, skills and qualifications so description and confirmation students written in their work road to put possible has been of mistakes prevention takes, to be realistically evaluated help will give.

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